

A pigeonpea + rice intercropping system for rainfed uplands

P. K. Mahapatra, Dryland Agriculture Research Project, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, Orissa, India

A replicated trial during 1984 and 1985 wet seasons tested the feasibility of pigeonpea + rice intercropping. Soil was laterite and sandy loam with pH 5.3, 0.04% total N, 18 kg available

P/ ha, 150 kg available K/ ha, and CEC 3.8 meq/100 g.

Pigeonpea cultivar R-60 (180 d) was grown in paired rows with 30 cm spacing. In the 90-cm spacing between 2 paired rows, 5 rows of rice cultivar Subhadra (90 d) were grown with 15 cm row-to-row spacing (see figure). The pigeonpea plant population was kept constant. Rice plant population varied because of less plot area in the intercrop. Pigeonpea received 20-18-17

kg NPK and rice received 60-18-17/ha.

Yields of pigeonpea only were 0.58-2 t/ha; of rice only, 1.74-2.58 t/ha. Intercrop pigeonpea yields were 0.52-1.7 t/ha; intercrop rice, 1.20-1.36 t/ha. The land equivalent ratio varied from 1.32 to 1.69. The intercrop yielded more than 50% of the pure rice crop yield and lost only 10-15% of the pure pigeonpea yield. This could make pigeonpea + rice feasible for rainfed uplands. □

Pigeonpea (P) + rice (R) intercropping system. Orissa, India.

Influence of zero-tillage on rice stem borer (SB) larval diapause in a rice - wheat cropping pattern

C. Inayatullah, A. Rahman, and A. Majid, National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad, and L. Khan, Entomology Department, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan

Larvae of yellow SB *Scirpophaga incertulus* (Wlk.) and white SB *S. innotata* (Wlk.) overwinter in rice

stubble; the adults emerge in Mar-Apr. Destruction of rice stubble after harvest and delaying planting to 20 May are recommended to control rice borers.

Rice - wheat is a common cropping pattern. The feasibility of directly drilled (zero-tillage) wheat in rice stubble was studied as a possible low-cost farm technology.

Wheat was drilled by tractor in 0.5-ha plots at 6 locations in Sheikupura

and Sialkot Districts during 1985-86. The check was wheat planted using conventional cultural practices (five cultivations).

A random sample of 500 rice tillers from the following rice crops was collected the first week of Feb. In direct-drilled wheat plots, the number of SB-infested tillers (12%) was significantly higher ($P = 0.05$) than in control plots (3%). In the direct-drilled wheat plots, there were 1-2 (mean 1.2)

live larvae/tiller, compared with 0-1 (mean 0.4) live larva/ tiller in check plots.

The increased carryover of larvae with zero-tillage wheat could be a

factor limiting the next year's rice crop, if nurseries are planted before 20 May. Zero-tillage wheat is safe to grow because *Scirpophaga* do not feed on wheat. *Sesamia inferens* (Wlk.) and

S. uniformis (Dudgn.) have been reported to attack rice and wheat in small numbers, but they could not be detected during this study.□

Rice-based cropping systems under irrigation in North India

P.C. Kharwara, P.K. Sharma, and L.N. Singh, Regional Research Station, Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishva Vidyalaya, Dhaulakuan, Dist. Sirmur (HP), India

Rice is becoming a more important crop during the Jun-Oct monsoon season in irrigated areas of North India because of its higher yield potential and better market price. It has even replaced maize in areas where soils are coarse textured with high permeability. We evaluated rice-based cropping systems for those areas.

A 1983-86 field trial included 9 crops fitted into 7 crop rotations: four 1-yr and three 2-yr. Soil was well-drained (saturated hydraulic conductivity 1 cm/h) sandy loam

Rice-equivalent yields and net returns from rice-based cropping systems evaluated in North India, 1983-86.

Rotation	Rice-equivalent grain yield (t/ha per yr)	Net return (\$/ha per yr)	Benefit-cost ratio
Rice - wheat ^a	9.9	500.00	1.22
Rice - linseed - black gram ^a	8.3	423.00	0.98
Rice - toria - wheat - black gram ^a	12.3	491.30	0.77
Rice - linseed - maize (fodder) ^a	10.8	532.50	1.28
Rice - sugarcane + wheat - potato - green gram ^b	13.1	413.90	0.53
Rice - toria - sugarcane - wheat - black gram ^b	10.2	416.70	0.80
Rice - wheat - sugarcane - potato - black gram ^b	15.4	524.20	0.59
CD (5%)	1.0	50.90	—

^aOne-year crop rotation. ^bTwo-year crop rotation.

(Fluvent) with neutral soil reaction and medium soil fertility.

A 2-yr rotation of rice - wheat - sugarcane - potato - black gram gave the highest rice-equivalent grain yield; rice - linseed - black gram gave the lowest (see table). Rice - wheat, the most popular crop rotation of the area, was next to last in grain production. The best 1-yr crop

rotation was rice - toria - wheat - black gram.

Rice - linseed - maize (fodder) gave the highest net returns, equal to rice - wheat, rice - toria - wheat - black gram, and rice - wheat - sugarcane - potato - black gram. The highest benefit-cost ratio was with rice - linseed - maize (fodder), followed by that with rice - wheat. □

ERRATA

D.K. Kundu, F.N. Ponnampereuma, and H.U. Neue. An improved method of representative sampling from aerobic soil solutions. 11 (6) (Dec 1986), 35-36.

The corrected article is reprinted below.

An improved method of sampling representative solutions from aerobic soils

D.K. Kundu, F.N. Ponnampereuma, and H. U. Neue, Soil Chemistry Department, IRRRI

Analysis of a solution collected in situ from aerobic soil can be used for characterizing the soil chemical

environment of upland rice. However, it is difficult to obtain samples from aerobic soils with moisture contents near field capacity (FC). The displacement method for well-packed FC moist soil columns has not been tested for validity under normal pot culture conditions. We evaluated samples collected by the conventional displacement method from three FC moist potted soils with different hydraulic conductivities.

Twelve kilograms each of air-dried (>2 mm sized) Luisiana clay, Maahas clay, and Pila loam soils were placed in 16-liter porcelain pots fitted at the bottom with drainage (coarse sintered glass) tubes. The soils were brought to FC moisture using tensiometers.

To collect soil solutions, 0.5% KSCN as displacing liquid was poured on the soil surfaces. The displaced solutions were drained into measuring cylinders. We tested the collected solutions for SCN-ion at regular intervals. Drops of acidic FeCl₃ solution were used as the indicator (a blood red-colored complex is formed).

From the fast-draining Luisiana clay and Pila loam soils, we could collect only 20-30 ml of soil solution. Beyond this volume, the leachate was diluted by the displacing liquid. In slow-draining Maahas clay, no displacement appeared in the first 200 ml. About 175 ml of soil solution is needed for a complete analysis; the displacement method was not appropriate for soils